

STYLISTIC FUNCTIONS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN MODERN ENGLISH

Tursunova Zebo Orif qizi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19109976>

Abstract

This thesis explores the stylistic functions of modern English phraseological units with the help of literary texts. Phraseological units, including idioms, set expressions, and proverbs, are integral components of the English lexicon, valued for their ability to convey meaning concisely, vividly, and expressively. This study examines how these units function stylistically to enhance expressiveness, evaluation, imagery, and characterization within texts with the help of contextual analysis method.

Key words:

English phraseological units, stylistic functions, literary discourse, expressiveness, contextual analysis.

Introduction

Phraseology is an independent linguistic discipline that occupies a central position at the intersection of lexicology, stylistics, semantics and pragmatics. It studies fixed or semi-fixed word combinations whose meaning is partially or fully transferred and not directly deducible from the meanings of their individual components. Such units include idioms, set expressions, collocations proverbs and sayings and are generally called as phraseological units in science [Kunin,1996]. Phraseological units (PUs) constitute an indispensable part in the lexical system of the English language, reflecting not only its structural organization, but also its cultural, emotional and expressive potential. In contemporary English, phraseological units are widely used in both spoken and written discourse, including literary texts, media, public speeches and everyday communication. Phraseological units are remarkably considered invaluable source from a stylistic point of view because they have expressive power and capacity to intensify emotional coloring, imagery, evaluation and pragmatic impact and play an important role in shaping author's individual style, character speech portrayal and the overall aesthetic effect of the text.

In literary discourse, English phraseological units especially function as markers emotional states, irony, evaluation and social identity. Writers deliberately choose them to achieve specific stylistic purposes such as emotiveness, expressiveness and stylistic contrast. In most cases phraseological units express the state of mind of the human being to what is happening within the world. In other words, expressiveness is respected as a sense of important information around culture and the mindset of individuals that phraseological units constitute [Gaybullayeva,2021].

In this paper, specific attention is paid to analyze the stylistic functions of phraseological units in modern English, focusing on their role in creating imagery, emotional coloring, expressive and evaluative impact in discourse. This contributes to a deeper understanding of how phraseological units function as stylistic devices beyond their nominative meaning.

Literature review.

The concept of phraseological units has been widely discussed in linguistic theory for many decades and a lot of foundational works on phraseology are mostly done by Russian linguists such as E. D. Polivanov, V. V. Vinogradov, N. N. Amosova, I. R. Galperin, A.V. Kunin and

others. One of the foundational figures in the study of phraseology is Swiss linguist Charles Bally (1865-1947) who founded the theory of phraseology and systematize word combinations in his works devoted to stylistics [Bally,1961]. According to his theory, word combinations are differentiated by the degree of their stability and divided them into two main groups: free combinations that lack stability and express a meaning from components and phraseological units which deprived of independent meaning of components. He emphasized the stability of word combinations with their emotional-expressive content in language. He compared word combinations to a chemical compound that means only when the components of such combinations are integrated together, they possess clear expressive meaning [Kunin,1996]. According to him, phraseological units sometimes can be equivalent to a simple word if they are commonly used in discourse. In later studies, the ideas of Ch. Bally became the basic foundation to the development of a theory of the equivalence of a phraseological unit to a word.

A systematic classification of phraseological units was proposed by V. V. Vinogradov, who distinguished between phraseological fusions, units and combinations based on the degree of semantic motivation. Vinogradov's approach made a significant influence on the later stylistic studies by proving how semantic cohesion affects expressive potential [Vinogradov,1977]]. Although his researches were applied to Russian phraseological studies, his theoretical framework has a huge impact on the development of English phraseology. There were noticeable gaps in English and Russian phraseology from the semantic and stylistic perspectives that's why this demanded a lot of investigations in modern English. In contemporary English linguistics, substantial contributions to phraseological theory development are connected with the names of famous Russian linguists: N. N. Amosova and A.V. Kunin. Their works remain central to the study of English phraseological units. N. N. Amosova introduced contextual approach to learn phraseological units and rejected the absolute semantic non-compositionality as the sole defining features of phraseological units [Amosova, 1963]. Unlike other scholars who emphasized idiomaticity as complete semantic opacity, she argued that many phraseological units keep a degree of semantic transparency and that their phraseological status can only be fully understood through contextual analysis. This idea was of great importance to study English phraseology, where many fixed expressions demonstrate partial motivation.

A.V. Kunin's contribution in modern English phraseology is that he defined phraseological units as stable combinations with transferred meaning and emphasizes their functional and stylistic characteristics due to an effect of Anthropocentric paradigm of modern linguistics. He identified expressiveness and emotional coloring as inherent properties of many phraseological units, which directly relates to their stylistic functions [Kunin,1969].

Methods and analysis.

This thesis employs contextual analysis introduced by N.N. Amosova (1963) to analyze and describe stylistic functions of English phraseological units extracted from modern English literary discourse. This is because the stylistic potential of phraseological units is primarily realized through context and literary texts are considered great sources of them. The most frequent stylistic functions of English phraseological units include expressive-imagery, emotional-expressive, evaluative and characterological function. It is essential to point out that the same phraseological unit can perform several functions above in the same context.

Expressive-imagery function

Expressive-imagery function of phraseological units (PUs) consists in the ability to create vivid, concrete and figurative image that enhance expressiveness and aesthetic impact of spoken and written discourse. Through imagery, phraseological units do not only name a situation or quality, but also depict it visually, making communication more vivid and memorable. This function is closely connected with metaphorical thinking and reflects human tendency to conceptualize abstract notions through physical images. This function of phraseological units is created on the basis of image-bearing stylistic devices such as metaphor, symbolism, hyperbole, allusion and others. This image helps the reader imagine the situation, not just understand it intellectually.

He must be as poor as a mouse in a church (S. Maugham).

This phraseological unit express the condition of extreme poverty, complete lack of money and possessions, not just ordinary poverty because it is impossible to find something to eat in a church where people come here only to worship. Its intensity creates visual image of harsh conditions of living, undernourishment and owning nothing on the individual's mind with the help of metaphorical imagery.

Emotional-expressive function.

Emotional-expressive function is central stylistic function of phraseological units (PUs) that refers to the ability to convey the speaker's emotions, attitudes and inner state more vividly than simple words. Instead of just describing emotions and feelings, a PU intensifies the psychological atmosphere and adds emotional depth to the context. This serves to evoke some emotions on the reader and feel the same things as the characters experience. Many linguists emphasize that emotional coloring of phraseological units is one of the defining features of phraseological meaning, making phraseological units especially productive in fiction, journalism and spoken discourse.

She was torn with grief at her loss (L. Tolstoy)

He lost his temper completely (M. Twain)

Both examples above express negative inner feelings of characters experiencing. Unlike lexical units, when authors give their characters' speech with the help of phraseological units, it influences also the reader's emotional state and makes them live in character's life, revealing character's inner world.

Evaluative function.

Evaluative nature of phraseological units (PUs) shows the ability to demonstrate the speaker's attitude, judgement or appraisal toward a person, object, action or situation. Through evaluation, PUs do not merely describe the reality but interpret it from a subjective point of view, indicating approval, disapproval, admiration or criticism. Evaluation in phraseology is usually implicit, embedded in the meaning of the whole unit, and inseparable from its semantic and stylistic structure [Galperin,1981].

Her purity was a pearl of great price (S. Maugham) – good virtues (positive)

Atticus said a good lawyer would cost an arm and leg, but it was worth every cent (H. Lee)
– extremely expensive (negative)

Characterological function.

Characterological function of phraseological units (PUs) is a stylistic function in which these expressions are used to reveal, define or emphasize the characters' personality traits, their temperament, moral qualities, education and social states in the literary texts or oral

discourse. In literature, authors use phraseological units to reveal their characters' quality instead of describing them directly. This function is created mostly with the help of metaphor and simile that based on similarity. It gives more expressive and detailed information rather than direct descriptions with neutral lexical units.

A green-eyed monster – extremely jealous person.

A wolf in sheep's clothing – selfish and cruel person.

The analysis of English phraseological units in literary texts confirms their pivotal role as stylistic and expressive resources. The article demonstrates that phraseological units perform multiple functions simultaneously, including expressive, evaluative, image-creating and characterizing functions. It is difficult to analyze these functions as separated from each other.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, English phraseological units are indispensable linguistic and stylistic tools that contribute significantly to the expressive, evaluative and aesthetic quality of English discourse. Through the analysis of literary texts and phraseological dictionaries, it has been established that these units are multifunctional: they convey emotional intensity, express subjective evaluations, generate vivid imagery and aid in characterizing speakers and literary figures. This mini research confirms that stylistic value of phraseological units emerges primarily from their contextual usage rather than from isolated semantic properties. This aligns with Amosova's contextual approach [1963], which emphasizes the importance of fixed lexical environments in shaping meaning and expressiveness.

Overall, the thesis demonstrates that English phraseological units are not only lexical source, but also dynamic, context-dependent elements of language that plays crucial role in stylistics, enhancing both aesthetic and communicative effects in modern English discourse.

References:

1. Амосова Н.Н. Основы английской фразеологии. – Ленинград: ЛГУ, 1963.
2. Bally, C. (1961). *Traite de stylistique francase*. Paris: Klincksieck
3. Cowie, A.P. (1990), *Oxford Dictionary of Current Idiomatic English*. Oxford: Oxford
4. University Press.
5. Cowie, A.P. (1998), *Phraseology: Theory, Analysis, and Applications*. Oxford: Oxford University press.
6. Dildora Fayzulla Kizi Gaybullayeva (2021). Universal and national peculiarities of phraseological description of image in the English and Uzbek languages. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2 (3), 990-998. doi: 10.24411/2181-1385-2021-00498
7. Galperin, I.R. (1981). *Stylistics*. Moscow: Higher School Publishing House.
8. Кунин А.В. Курс фразеологии современного английского языка. Издание
9. второе. – М., 1996.
10. Kunin, A. V. (1969). *Osnovniye ponyatiya frazeologicheskoy stilitistiki* (Basic
11. concepts of phraseological stylistics). Moskva: Moskovskiy pedagogicheskiy institut inostrannykh yazykov imeni M. Toreza.
12. Vinogradov, V.V. (1977). *Selected works: Lexicology and Lexicography*. Moscow: Nauka